

Connectivity in Europe

Between 2016 and 2021 it grew by 72.84% in the Desi countries

Desi Index calculates the value of connectivity. This variable is constituted as a sum between several four under variables or Fixed Broadband Take Up, Fixed Broadband Coverage, Broadband Mobile, and Broadband Prices. In analytical form it is possible to calculate connectivity as indicated below:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Connectivity}_{it} &= \text{FixedBroadbandTakeUp}_{it} + \text{FixedBroadbandCoverage}_{it} \\ &+ \text{MobileBroadband}_{it} + \text{BroadbandPrices}_{it} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{FixedBroadbandTakeUp}_{it} &= \text{OverallFixedBroadbandTakeUp}_{it} \\ &+ \text{AtLeast100MbpsFixedBroadbandTakeUp}_{it} + \text{AtLeast1GbpsTakeUp}_{it} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{FixedBroadbandCoverage}_{it} &= \text{FastBroadbandCoverage}_{it} + \text{FixedVeryHighCapacityNetworkCoverage}_{it} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{MobileBroadband}_{it} &= \text{4GCoverage}_{it} + \text{5GReadiness}_{it} + \text{5GCoverage}_{it} \\ &+ \text{MobileBroadbandTakeUp}_{it} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{BroadbandPrices}_{it} = \text{BroadbandPriceIndex}_{it}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Connectivity}_{it} &= \text{OverallFixedBroadbandTakeUp}_{it} \\ &+ \text{AtLeast100MbpsFixedBroadbandTakeUp}_{it} + \text{AtLeast1GbpsTakeUp}_{it} \\ &+ \text{FastBroadbandCoverage}_{it} + \text{FixedVeryHighCapacityNetworkCoverage}_{it} \\ &+ \text{4GCoverage}_{it} + \text{5GReadiness}_{it} + \text{5GCoverage}_{it} \\ &+ \text{MobileBroadbandTakeUp}_{it} + \text{BroadbandPriceIndex}_{it} \end{aligned}$$

Where $i=27$ e $t=[2016;2021]$.

Ranking of countries by connectivity value in 2021. Denmark is in the first place for the value of connectivity with a value of 18.50, followed by the Netherlands with a value of 17.11 and Spain with a value of 15,50 units. In the middle of the standings there are Finland with a value of 12.81, followed by Latvia with an amount of 12.59 and from Portugal with a value of 12.13. Lithuania with a value of 10.42 close the ranking, followed by Bulgaria with a value of 9.52 and Greece with a value of 9.43.

Ranking of countries by the percentage variation of connectivity between 2016 and 2021. Greece is in the first place for the value of the percentage variation of connectivity with a value of 145.87% equal to an amount of 5.60 units, followed From Ireland with a value equal to 132.36% equal to an amount of 8.03 units and from Cyprus with a value of 125.90 equal to an amount of 5.83 units. In the middle of the standings there are Germany with an amount equal to 82.91% equal to an amount of 6.57 units, followed by Bulgaria with a value of 76.17% equal to an amount of 4.12 units, and from Hungary with a value of 74.91% equal to an amount of 5.57 units. Lithuania closes the ranking with

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a value of 38.99% equal to an amount of 2.93 units, followed by Estonia with a value of 33.47% equal to an amount of 2.292 units and from the Latvia with a value of 18.51% equal to an amount of 1.97 units.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Below is a clusterization using the K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. The analysis shows the presence of two Clusters or:

- Cluster 1: Netherlands, Denmark, Sweden, Romania, Latvia, Luxembourg, Slovenia, Estonia, Portugal, Malta, Germany, Hungary, Finland, Lithuania;
- Cluster 2: Croatia, Bulgaria, Ireland, Poland, Italy, Cyprus, Austria, Slovakia, Greece, Czech Republic, France, Belgium.

From the point of view of the median value of connectivity for clusters it is possible to identify the following system of the Clusters or: $C1 = 13.29 > C2 = 11.32$. From the point of view of the geographical representation of the Clusters not possible to recognize a contrast between central-north Europe and central-southern Europe, as in the dominant cluster, or in the Cluster C1, there are both Central Europe countries, and Eastern European countries that countries of northern Europe. It follows then that the choice whether or not to invest in connectivity, which is evidently a choice that refers to the investment in the networks, depends on strictly political-institutional factors rather than on geographical-territorial-apartment conditions. In particular, it is necessary to underline the good performance in terms of connectivity of Estonia, Romania, Latvia, Hungary and Lithuania, which through the investment of networks have increased the chances of making its economy more dynamic and productive.

Network Analysis with Manhattan distance. Below are the data analyzed using the approach to the network analysis with Manhattan distance. Specifically, using this tool it is possible to identify the presence of some complex structures and some simplified structures in terms of connections between the various countries. There is a connection between Finland, Germany, Portugal, Bulgaria, and Malta. In particular:

- Finland is associated with Germany with a link having a value of 0.21;
- Germany is associated with Bulgaria with a link having a value of 0.29 and Finland with a connection having a value of 0.21;
- Bulgaria is associated with Germany with a value of 0.29, to Portugal for a value of 0.44 units and the mortar with a value of 0.38;
- Portugal is associated with Bulgaria with a link having a value of 0.44;
- Malta is associated with Bulgaria with a link having a value of 0.38 units.

There is a complex relationship between Latvia, Luxembourg, Denmark and Sweden. In particular:

- Latvia is associated with Luxembourg for a value of 0.47;
- Luxembourg is associated with Denmark for a value of 0.38 and Latvia with a value of 0.47;
- Denmark is associated with Luxembourg with a link having a value of 0.38 and Sweden with a link having a value of 0.25;
- Sweden is associated with Denmark with a link having a value of 0.25 units.

There is also a complex structure between Austria, Slovakia and the Czech Republic. Specifically:

- Austria is connected to Slovakia with a link having a value of 0.4 and the Czech Republic with a link having a value of 0.32;

- The Czech Republic is connected to Austria with a value of 0.32 and Slovakia for an equal value 0.42;
- Slovakia is connected to the Czech Republic with a link having a value of 0.42 and to Austria with a link having a value of 0.4.

Finally there are two different simplified structures as identified below or:

- Estonia has a connection with Slovenia for a value of 0.22;
- Poland has a connection with Ireland for a value of 0.18 units.

Conclusions. The value of connectivity grew on an average of 72.84% between 2016 and 2021 in the European countries indicated by Desi. It should be considered that the growth of connectivity is a prerequisite for the establishment of an economic of knowledge and a real digital economy. It therefore derives that through the enhancement of the networks the foundations for future economic growth in European countries are placed. Certainly the Cluster Analysis highlights how among the high level of connectivity there are also countries of Eastern Europe and this phenomenon opens the possibility for those countries to experience further economic growth. However, we must also emphasize that to ensure that the economy of technological innovation can develop it is not enough to invest in networks, as regards the contrary it is also necessary to invest in human capital. In fact, human capital is able to make sure that the proposed digital infrastructure can be able to generate added value with the creation of new businesses, start -ups, New Cos, and the like. It is therefore necessary to adequately balance the investment in the networks, or the growth of connectivity, with the formation of human capital in the STEM disciplines and in the economic-safe sciences, to ensure that a culture of entrepreneurial is widespread capable of maximizing the value of infrastructure investments. Finally, it is also necessary to consider the role of institutions and economic policies in creating the conditions to facilitate the establishment of companies. In fact, as demonstrated for example by the case of Ireland, it is necessary to accompany investment policies in networks and digital structures with adequate tax policies that can make it convenient to develop the new business activities to a more agile extent from the point of view of taxation. Finally, some role is also played by the presence of external forms of financing that can help digital companies to grow. In this sense, the presence of Capital Ventures, of Business Angels, and of real financial rounds is aimed at digital startups is necessary to ensure that Europe is competitive in the economy of knowledge also in the scenario of the contrast between USA and China.

Declarations

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Appendix

	2021	Countries	Cluster	Silhouette
7	18.5098	Denmark	C1	0.67591
8	11.6392	Estonia	C1	0.641582
9	12.817	Finland	C1	0.59234
11	14.499	Germany	C1	0.59892
13	12.9993	Hungary	C1	0.598225
16	12.5948	Latvia	C1	0.671368
17	10.4285	Lithuania	C1	0.50708
18	15.2424	Luxembourg	C1	0.668032
19	13.5281	Malta	C1	0.61645
20	17.111	Netherlands	C1	0.676812
22	12.1309	Portugal	C1	0.620406
23	13.2932	Romania	C1	0.672717
25	13.2982	Slovenia	C1	0.651631
26	15.5073	Spain	C1	0.671593
27	14.8928	Sweden	C1	0.67461
1	13.2476	Austria	C2	0.673569
2	12.0994	Belgium	C2	0.531547
3	9.5241	Bulgaria	C2	0.685516
4	11.3528	Croatia	C2	0.689179
5	10.4539	Cyprus	C2	0.674206
6	11.1606	Czechia	C2	0.644593
10	11.8522	France	C2	0.61998
12	9.43265	Greece	C2	0.649056
14	14.1027	Ireland	C2	0.684704
15	10.5877	Italy	C2	0.680356
21	11.3289	Poland	C2	0.683503
24	11.5633	Slovakia	C2	0.66053